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A REVIEW ON TOPICAL LIPOSOMES: A NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This review will highlight work done in our laboratories formulating and evaluating topical liposomal delivery is a mostly used both in vivo and in vitro methods by using animal models. The recent therapeutic work done on drug delivery using Topical Liposomes as carrier for small and large molecules. Topical Liposomes are solid colloidal particles in size from 10nm-1000nm. They are sphere shaped vesicles made up of one or more phospholipid bilayers. It shows greater affinity towards horny layer of skin and penetrates skin deeper tissues with more absorption rate. When topical liposomes are applied on the skin, they act as a solubilizing matrix for poorly soluble drugs and reduce the side effects of these drugs. Topical liposome formulations are more effective and less toxic than conventional formulations (Tablets, capsules etc.). They also alter and improve pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties of less efficacious drugs. This review discusses the potential advantages in topical drug delivery, mechanism of action, method of preparation, characterization and application of Topical Liposomes drug delivery system.

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INTRODUCTION

Various methods are applicable for many diseases, but topical route is most used. Conventional dosage forms provide drug release immediately and it cause fluctuation of drug level in blood depending upon dosage form. Over the past few decades, the techniques to develop newer drug delivery system have tried not only to address the major issue of prolonged and controlled drug delivery but also to achieve targeted drug delivery. These approaches are expected to provide maximum therapeutic benefits with minimal adverse effects. Liposomes are a tiny bubble (vesicle), in shaped which are made up of same material as cell membrane. It is a novel generation of carrier mediated drug delivery system having several advantages over other conventional methods. The name liposome is derived from two Greekwords: 'Lipos' meaning fat and 'Soma' meaning body. The conventional liposomes are simple vesicles consisting of outer bilayer of lipids enclosing a central aqueous core. Because of this unique structure, they can entrap both the hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs [1]. Besides this particular advantage, liposomes are biocompatible, biodegradable and non-toxic. They are of sufficient flexibility to allow synthesis in various sizes and can be formulated as eye drops, gels and ointments for topical delivery. However, the conventional liposomes had the disadvantage of being unstable, getting aggregated and were susceptible to phagocytosis. In order to overcome these problems and to achieve prolonged and targeted drug delivery, a whole new generation of liposomes has evolved. The application of Liposomes in skin treatment is based on the convenience that the spherical vesicles may encapsulate a wide range of active ingredients. Furthermore, the bilayer structure of lipid vesicles has similarity to that of cellular membranes. As a result of this similarity, the liposomes are able to interact with the cutaneous cells in different ways, such as endocytosis, fusion, or exchange of lipids. The latter has a specific impact in topical preparations and dermocosmetics, since it may alter the physical properties of the skin. Liposomes are used in skin gels and skin creams as a cosmetic product.. Vegetable phospholipids are widely used for topical applications in cosmetics and dermatology, since they have a high content of esterified essential fatty acids ,especially linoleic acid which is believed to increase the barrier function of the skin and decrease water loss within a short period of time after application [2]. Why there is any need for liposomes as new drug carrier systems with topical dermatics? The major problem concerning the efficacy of topical drug is that they have to reach the site of action and to stay there in an effective concentration for a certain time. Although the skin belongs to the organs which can be reached directly drug application on the skin surface does not automatically mean the drug getting to the right site of action. This in fact is the problem with the conventional dosage forms like creams and ointments. The use of penetration enhancers, e.g. dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) or propylene glycol leads, on the one hand, to an improved transport rate through the epidermal barrier but, on the other to more unwanted effects due to an increases systemic drug level. Moreover irritative or even toxic side effects are reported leading to the conclusion that addition of penetration enhancers does not really mean an improvement in topical drug administration. Topical drug delivery system, designed to deliver a variety of drugs to the body through diffusion across the skin layers, is appealing for several reasons including avoidance of the variable absorption and metabolic breakdown associated with oral treatments, drug administration can be continuous, and minimal intestinal irritation can be avoided [30].

Advantages [1-6]

- Liposomal drug delivery system offers protection from the external environment condition like (temperature, humidity).
- Liposome release the drug at the slower rate so as to provide prolonged release/sustained release to the skin.
- According to studies performed so far liposomes are biodegradable and non-toxic which is important to avoid side effects.
- They are similar to epidermis with respect to their lipid composition which enables them to penetrate the epidermal barrier to a greater extent compared to other dosage form.
- Loading of drug into liposomal vesicles offers reduction in side effects.
- Both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs are incorporated in topical liposomes.
- Increased solubility of the drug.
- To achieve active targeting.
- To enhance the efficacy and therapeutic index of drug.

Classification of Topical Liposomes [7,8,28]

Size of topical liposome can vary from very small (0.025 μm) to large (2.5 μm) vesicles. Topical liposomes may have one or bilayer membranes. Both size and number of bilayers affect the amount of drug encapsulation in the topical liposomes. On the basis of their size and number of bilayers, liposomes can also be classified into one of various categories:

Based on structural parameters

- Multilamellar Vesicles (MLV)
- Stable Plurilamellar Vesicles (SPLV)
- Frozen And Thawed MLV (FATMLV)
- Vesicles prepared by Extrusion Technique (VET)
- Dehydration Rehydration Method (DRV)

Based on method of liposome Preparation

- Multilamellar Large Vesicles (MLV) >0.5 μm
- Oligolamellar Vesicles (OLV) 0.1-1 μm
- Unilamellar Vesicles (UV) all size range
- Small unilamellar Vesicles (SUV) 20-100 nm
- Medium sized Unilamellar Vesicles (MUV)
- Large Unilamellar Vesicles (LUV) >100 nm
- Giant Unilamellar Vesicles (GUV) >1 μm
- Multivesicular Vesicles (MV) >1 μm

Based upon composition

- Conventional Liposomes (Neutral or Negatively charged Phospholipids and Cholesterol)
- Fusogenic Liposomes (Reconstituted Sendai Virus Envelopes)
- pH sensitive Liposomes (Phospholipid such as PE or DOPE with either CHEMS or OA)
- Cationic Liposomes (Cationic lipids with DOPE)
- Long Circulatory Liposomes (Neutral high temperature , Cholesterol and 5-10% of PEG-DSPE)
- Immuno Liposomes (CL or LCL with attached monoclonal antibody or recognition sequence)

THE STRUCTURE OF SKIN

The skin is the largest organ of the body, accounting for about 15% of the total adult body weight. It performs many vital functions, including protection against external physical, chemical and biologic assailants, as well as prevention of excess water loss from the body. The integumentary system is formed by the skin and its derivative structures (Figure 1). The skin has a made up of three layers: the epidermis, the dermis, and subcutaneous tissue [9]. The outermost level, the epidermis, consists of specific constellation of cells known as keratinocytes, which function is to synthesize keratin, a long, thread like protein with a protective role. The middle layer, the Dermis, is the fundamentally made up of the fibrillar structural protein known as collagen. The dermis lies on the subcutaneous tissue, on panniculus, which contain small lobes of fat cells known as lipocytes.

Figure 1: Structure of skin.

Epidermis

The Epidermis is stratified, squamous epithelium layer that is composed primarily of two types of cells: Keratinocytes and Dendritic cells. The epidermis commonly divided into four layers according to Keratinocyte morphology and position as they differentiate into horny cells, including the basal cell layer (stratum germinativum), the squamous cell layer (stratum spinosum) the granular cell layer (stratum granulosum) and the cornified or horny cell layer (stratum corneum)[10]. The epidermis is a continually renewing layer and give rise to derivative structures, such as pilosebaceous apparatuses, nails, and sweat glands. The basal cells of the epidermis undergo proliferation cycles that provide for the renewal of the outer epidermis. Keratinocytes is 80% of cells in the epidermis are the ectodermally derived keratinocytes. The differentiation process that occurs as the cell migrate from the basal layer to the surface of the skin results in keratinization, a process in which the keratinocyte first passes through a synthetic and then a degradative phase [11]. In the synthetic phase, the cells builds up a cytoplasmic supply of keratin a fibrous intermediate filament arranged in an alpha – helical coil pattern that serves as part of the cells' cytoskeleton. Bundles of these keratin filaments converge on and terminate at the plasma membrane forming the intercellular attachment plates known as desmosomes. During the degradative phase of Keratinization, cellular organelles are lost, the content of the cell are consolidated of the mixture of filament sand amorphous cell envelopes, and the cell finally is known as a horny cell or corneocyte. The process of maturation resulting in cell death is called as terminal differentiation. The basal layer, also known as the stratum germinativum, contains column-shaped Keratinocytes that attach to the basement membrane zone with their long axis perpendicular to the dermis. The basal cells form a single layer and adhere to one another as well as to more superficial squamous cells or stratum spinosum. Granular Layer is most superficial layer of the epidermis containing living cells, the granular layer or stratum granulosum, is composed of flattened cells holding abundant keratohyaline

granules in their cytoplasm. These cells are responsible for further synthesis and modification of proteins involved in keratinization. A lysosomal enzyme present only in small amounts in the stratum basale and stratum spinosum are found at high levels in the stratum granulosum because the granular layer is a keratogenous zone of the epidermis. Horny cells of the cornified layer provide mechanical protection to the underlying epidermis and a barrier to prevent water loss and invasion by foreign substances. The melanocyte is a dendrite, pigment – synthesizing cells derived from the crest in the confined in the skin predominantly in the basal layer. Melanocytes are responsible for the production of the pigment melanin and its transfer to keratinocytes. Langerhans cells are involved in a variety of T-cell responses. The cells mainly are distributed in the squamous and granular layers with fewer cells in the basal layer. These cells must recognize and process soluble antigen found in epidermal tissue. The cells are dendritic and do not form cellular junctions with neighbouring cells. Hair Follicles have many valuable biologic functions including protection from the elements and distribution of sweat gland products. Hair follicles vary considerably in size and shape, depending on their location, but they all have the same basic structure. Sebaceous glands are found in greatest number on the face and scalp but are present on nearly all other locations of the body with the exception of the tarsal plate eyelids, the buccal mucosa etc. Cells of the sebaceous glands contain abundant lipid droplets known as sebum in their cytoplasm and are arranged into lobules off the upper segment of the hair follicle [12].

Dermis [11]

The dermis is an integrated system of fibrous, filamentous, and amorphous connective tissue that accommodated stimulus-induced entry by nerve and vascular networks, epidermally derived appendages, fibroblasts, macrophages and mast cells. The dermis layer provides its pliability, elasticity and tensile strength. It protects the body from mechanical injury, binds water, aids in thermal regulation, and includes receptors of sensory stimuli. The principal component of the dermis is collagen. A major structural protein for the entire body, collagen is found in tendons, ligaments, the lining of the bones, and the dermis [8]. Collagen is a major stress-resistant material of the skin. Mast cells are specialized secretory cells derived from bone marrow and distributed in connective tissues throughout the body. In the normal dermis, mast cells appear as oval to spindle-shaped cells with a centrally located round to oval nucleus. Mast cells are playing a active role in many conditions such as allergy, parasitic diseases, atherosclerosis, malignancy, asthma, pulmonary fibrosis and arthritis.

MECHANISM OF ACTION OF TOPICAL LIPOSOMES [13,14]

A liposomal formulation to be effective, especially for hydrophilic drugs, it is essential that the suspension undergo significant dehydration. Since in most studies reported the lipid concentration scarcely exceeds 100mg/ml, the bulk aqueous medium constitutes roughly 90% of the formulation. Thus without a high degree of dehydration, no advantages over simple aqueous solution can be governed by employing liposomal systems, especially, if the drug action is anticipated to occur within few hours after application. The dehydration of liposomal suspension can either be complete or reach an equilibrium stage within the bilayers.

Hydrophobic drugs-

A major fraction of the added drug would be encapsulated or intercalated within the lipid bilayers of the liposomes. Further, optimum loading of hydrophobic drugs would be possible only if the lipid bilayers are maintained above the T_m of the major lipid the transfer of drug from lipid bilayers into skin can occur as long as the bilayer are in liquid crystalline state. If the liquid crystalline phase is altered to the gel state, transport of the drug low. Thus, the extent of dehydration will determine if changes in the state of the liposomal bilayers from a liquid crystalline phase to the gel state are possible. A second consequence of dehydration involves the formation of a strong adhesive patch of liposomal bilayer on the skin.

Hydrophilic drug-

The mode of action for liposomal transport of hydrophilic drugs parallels that for hydrophobic drug in qualitative manner. This is strictly because of major role of the water associated with the bilayers upon dehydration of the liposomal suspension. Thus for liposomal systems that retain a constant amount of water within the bilayers following dehydration to an equilibrium state, drug transport would continue over extended periods of time.

The follicular option [3] –

The mechanism described above occurs regardless of the presence or absence of follicles in the skin specimen however, when a follicular pathway is available, upon dehydration the liposomal bilayers can partition and pack into the follicular or hair ducts. This partitioning is favorable since the follicular ducts contain lipids. The filling of the follicular opening with the liposomal bilayers not only results in entrapped drugs being carried into the follicles but also allows partitioning of untrapped drugs into the bilayer matrix within follicles.

METHOD AND PREPARATION OF TOPICAL LIPOSOME [8,15,16]

The main goal of an ideal method of liposome formulation is to obtain efficient drug entrapment, narrow particles size distribution and long term stability of liposome products. The general procedure for all methods of liposomes preparation involves hydrating of the lipid, followed by sizing of the particles and removing of the non encapsulated drug. There are two types used for the preparation of liposomes: passive loading and active loading method. The most common used methods in the preparation for liposomes are: thin-film hydration method, microemulsification, sonication, membrane extrusion, freeze thawed method, ether injection method, ethanol injection method, reverse phase evaporation method, dehydration-rehydration, and calcium-induced fusion method.

Figure.2: Methods of Liposomes Preparations.

Various types of compounds with ionizable groups, and those which display both lipid and water solubility, can be introduced into the liposomes after the formation of intact vesicles. Preparations and methods of topical liposomes shown in Figure: 2.

Passive Loading Techniques –

This technique include three different groups of methods such as mechanical dispersion, solvent dispersion and detergent solubilization. In the passive loading method the drug is encapsulated by introducing an aqueous phase of a water-soluble drug or an organic phase of a lipid-soluble drug before or at some stage during the preparation of the topical liposomes

Active loading Techniques [8] –

In the active loading method, the drugs can be loaded by creating diffusion gradients for the ions or drugs across the external and internal aqueous phases shown Figure 3. Two processes generate this pH imbalance and active (remote) loading.

- Liposomes are prepared in low pH solution
- Addition of the base to extraliposomal medium.
- Several methods exist for improved loading of the drugs, including remote (active) loading methods which load drug molecules into preformed liposomes using pH ingredients and potential difference across liposomal membranes.

Figure 3: Active Loading Technique.

Advantages over passive encapsulation techniques:

- ✓ Increase encapsulation efficiency and capacity.
- ✓ Less leakage of the encapsulated compounds.
- ✓ Use of constitutive lipids, as drug is loaded after the formation of carrier units.

Mechanical dispersion methods -

Film hydration method [8,17] –

It is the simplest technique for the liposome formation but its use is limited because of its low encapsulation efficiency. This method produces liposomes by hydrating thin lipid films shown in figure 4 deposited from organic solution on a glass wall by shaking at temperatures above T_c (Transition temperature). The solvent is removed at reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator. The dry film of lipids which has been deposited onto the wall of a round bottom flask is hydrated by adding a drug solution with a water soluble marker. As the lipid becomes hydrated and starts to form into closed vesicles only a small amount of the solute becomes entrapped. This method yields a heterogeneous sized population of Multilamellar large vesicles over $1\mu\text{m}$ in diameter. Then the prepared liposome is further sonicated by using sonicator to form small unilamellar vesicles.

Figure 4: Film Hydration Method.

French Pressure cell [8]–

This is very useful method developed in extrusion of preformed large topical liposomes in a French press under very high pressure. Topical liposomes rather uni- or oligo-lamellar intermediate size is prepared by this method (30-80 nm in diameter depending on the applied pressure). Topical liposomes are more stability as compared to sonicated liposomes. Disadvantages of this method is mainly cost is very high that consists of an electric hydraulic press and pressure cell (Figure.6). Advantages of this method are less structural defects, method is simple, rapid and reproducible.

Figure 6: French Pressure Cell.

Microemulsification liposomes [8]–

This method is used to prepare small Micro lamellar Vesicles from concentrated lipid dispersion. Micro fluidizer pumps the fluid at very high pressure through a 5 μ m orifice. The lipids can be introduced into the fluidizer, either as a dispersion of large Multilamellar Vesicles, or as slurry of unhydrated lipid in an organic medium, fluid is collected and can be recycled through the pump until vesicles of the spherical dimension are obtained (Figure.6).

Figure 6: Use of Micro-Fluidizer to prepare SUVs from MLVs.

After a single pass, the size of vesicles is reduced to a size 0.1 and 0.2µm in diameter. The exact size distribution, its depends on the nature of the components of the membrane and hydration medium. The presence of negative lipids tends to decrease their size, while increasing cholesterol concentration gives larger liposomes. This process is efficient for encapsulation of water-soluble materials.

Membrane Extrusion Techniques [15] –

Liposomes passed through membrane of defined pore size and lower pressure is required (<100 psi) and LUVs as well as MLVs is prepared. The Vesicle contents are exchanged with dispersion medium during breaking and resealing of phospholipid bilayers as they pass through the polycarbonate membrane. For high entrapment, the water soluble compounds should be present in suspending medium during the extrusion process.

Figure 7: Liposomes preparation using Extrusion Technique.

Dried reconstituted Vesicles (DRVs) –

This method starts with freeze drying of a dispersion of empty SUVs and then rehydrating it with the aqueous fluid containing the materials to be entrapped. This leads to a dispersion of solid lipids in finely subdivided form. The step of freeze drying is used to freeze and lyophilize a preformed SUVs dispersion rather than to dry the lipids from an organic solution. This leads to an organized membrane structure as compared to random matrix structure, which on addition of water (one tenth the volume of the original SUVs) can rehydrate, fuse and reseal to form vesicles with high capture efficiency (Figure 8). The water soluble materials to be entrapped are added to the dispersion of empty SUVs and they are dried together, so the material for inclusion is present in the dried precursor lipid before the final step of addition of aqueous medium[15].

Figure 8: Preparation of dried – Reconstituted vesicles (DRVs).

Freeze Thaw Sonication method (FTS)–

The method is based on freezing of a unilamellar dispersion & then thawing at room temperature for 15min. SUVs are rapidly frozen and thawed slowly. The short-lived sonication disperses aggregated materials to LUV. The creation of unilamellar vesicles is as a result of the fusion of SUV throughout the processes of freezing and thawing. This type of synthesis is strongly inhibited by increasing the phospholipid concentration and by increasing the ionic strength of the medium. The encapsulation efficacies from 20% to 30% were obtained.

Solvent dispersion method

This method can be categorized on the basis of the miscibility of the organic solvent and aqueous solution. These include the conditions where organic solvent is miscible with the aqueous phase; the organic solvent is immiscible with the aqueous phase, the later being in excess; and the cases where the organic solvent in excess, and immiscible with the aqueous phase.

Ethanol injection method-

A lipid solution of ethanol is rapidly injected into an excess of saline or other aqueous medium. The rate of the injection is usually sufficient to achieve complete mixing, The MLVs are immediately formed. (Figure.9). This method is extremely simple and has low risk of degradation of sensitive lipids. The disadvantage of this method is to difficult remove residual ethanol from phospholipids membrane. Liposomes are very dilute, it is difficult to remove all ethanol because it forms azeotrope with water and the possibility of various biologically active macromolecules to inactivation in the presence of even low amounts of ethanol.

Figure 9: Preparation of Ethanol Injection.

Ether injection-

A solution of lipids dissolved in diethyl ether or ether/methanol mixture is slowly injected to an aqueous solution of the material to be encapsulated at 55-65°C or under reduced pressure Figure 10. Removal of ether under vacuum leads to the formation of liposomes. The drawbacks of the technique are this process is time consuming and the exposure of compounds to be encapsulated to organic solvents or high temperature [15].

Figure 10: Preparation of Ether Injection.

Reverse phase evaporation method [8,29] –

In this method water in oil emulsion is formed by sonication of a two phase system containing phospholipids in organic solvent (diethyl ether or isopropyl ether or mixture of isopropyl ether and chloroform) and aqueous buffer. The organic solvents are removed under reduced pressure, resulting in the formation of a viscous gel. The liposomes are formed when residual solvent is removed by continued rotary evaporation under reduced pressure. Advantage of this method high encapsulation efficiency up to 65% can be obtained in a medium of low ionic strength for example 0.01M NaCl. The method has been used to encapsulate small and large macromolecules. The main disadvantage of the method is the exposure of the materials to be encapsulated to organic solvents.

Double emulsion vesicles –

In this process, an active ingredient is first dissolved in an aqueous phase which is then emulsified in an organic solvent of a polymer to make a primary w/o emulsion. This primary emulsion is further mixed in an emulsifier-containing aqueous solution to make a w/o/w double emulsion. These vesicles with aqueous core are suspended in aqueous medium, the two aqueous compartments being separated from each other by a pair of phospholipid monolayer's whose hydrophobic surfaces face each other across a thin film of organic solvent. Removal of this solvent clearly results in an intermediate sized unilamellar vesicle. The organic solvent is evaporated using strong jet of nitrogen thus forming double emulsion. The last traces of organic solvent are removed by evaporation and finally the volume is adjusted by adding extra distilled water and then the product is centrifuged at 20 °C For 30 min. at 37,000 g to remove lipid aggregates [8,15].

Detergent removal Methods [31]

The detergents at their critical micelles concentrations have been used to solubilize lipids. As the detergent is removed the micelles become progressively richer in phospholipid and finally combine to form LUVs. They are certainly the best methods for preparing liposomes with lipophilic proteins inserted into the membranes. Three methods are applied for the removal of detergent such as Dialysis, Column chromatography and the Bio - beads.

Dialysis –

In this method higher CMC indicates that the equilibrium is strongly shifted towards the bulk solution, so that removal from the mixed membrane by dialysis becomes relatively easy. Detergents commonly used for this purpose exhibit reasonably high CMC (-10-20mM) so that their removal is facilitated.

Column Chromatography-

Removal of detergents using Gel Chromatography involving a column of Sephadex G-25

Detergent Adsorption using Bio-beads –

The ability of biobeads SM-2, to adsorb Triton X-100 selectively and rapidly, makes them a suitable candidate for LUV preparation by detergent solubilization method. On hydrating the casted lipid film with 0.5-1.0% Triton X-100, Bio-beads are added to the dispersion (0.3g wet Bio-beads per ml of dispersion) and rocked for about 2h at 4±1 C.

INCORPORATION OF LIPOSOMES INTO THE GEL MATRIX

Liposomes can be incorporated into gel to enhance their retention time on the skin. The liposomal gel provides higher and sustained concentrations of drug in skin at the same time do not enhance the systemic absorption of drugs. Hence adverse effects of many drugs can be minimized [18].

EVALUATION OF TOPICAL LIPOSOMES [8,19-24,27]**Particle size**

Both particle size and particle size distribution of liposomes influence their physical stability. These can be determined by the following method. a) Laser light scattering b) Transmission electron microscopy. By the electron microscopy like SEM (Scanning electron microscopy) and TEM (Transmission electron microscopy) the size of the liposomal vesicles can precisely characterized. Laser light scattering is one of the simplest methods to determine the size and the size distribution of the vesicles.

Surface Charge –

The positive, negative or neutral charge on the surface of the liposomes is due to the composition of the head groups. The surface charge of liposomes governs the kinetic and extent of distribution in vivo, as well as interaction with the target cells. The method involved in the measurement of surface charge is based on free-flow electrophoresis of MLVs. In general two methods are used to assess the charge, namely free-flow electrophoresis and zeta potential measurement. From the mobility of the liposomal dispersion in a suitable buffer, the surface charge on the vesicles can be calculated.

pH Optimization –

The pH of gel is important parameter which are detected at a different pH values, 5.5;6.5 and 7.5 using pH meter.

Viscosity and Rheological properties –

The rheological analysis of the experimental liposomal gel was performed using a Brookfield viscometer.

Drug content and content uniformity – Drug content and content uniformity:

The gel sample (100mg) was withdrawn and drug content was determined using UV spectrophotometer. In case of liposomal gel, it was shaken with sufficient quantity of methanol to extract the drug and then analyzed by using UV spectrophotometer [27].

In-vitro skin permeation analysis-

A biological membrane is used as a model membrane for the skin permeation study because of its similarity to human skin in lipid content and permeability. The skin samples were mounted between the two half-cells of a side-by-side diffusion chamber with a 37°C water jacket to control the temperature. The dorsal surface of the skin was placed in contact with the donor chamber, which was filled with the liposome formulation. The receptor chamber was filled with 0.1 M PBS (pH 7.4) and stirred with a star-head Teflon magnetic bar driven by a synchronous motor. At time intervals of 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 8 and, 24 h, a 1 mL aliquot of receptor was withdrawn, and the same volume of fresh medium was added back into the chamber. The sample was analyzed by HPLC. The cumulative amount was plotted against time. The steady-state flux was determined as the slope of linear portion of the plot. Lag time was also obtained by extrapolating the linear portion of the penetration profile to the abscissa.

Stability studies –

The ability of vesicles to retain the drug was assessed by keeping the liposomal suspension and liposomal gel at different temperature conditions, i.e. 4-5°C (Refrigerator; RF), 25±2 °C (Room temperature; RT) and 37±2 °C for a period of 56 days. The liposomal suspension was kept in sealed vials (20 ml capacity) after flushing with nitrogen. Samples were withdrawn periodically and analyzed for drug content, in the manner described under drug entrapment efficiency and particle size distribution studies.

Encapsulation Efficiency [25] and trapped volume –

Encapsulation efficiency is an expression of the amount of drug incorporated into the liposome and is normally defined as the percentage of drug bound to liposomes relative the total amount of drug. Determination of this parameter generally requires separation of free drug from the liposomal formulation. Analysis of drug in both the free and encapsulated drug fractions allow calculation of encapsulation efficiency. The encapsulation efficiency was expressed as the percent of drug encapsulated and calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Encapsulation Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{C_d - C_f}{C_d} \times 100$$

Where,

C_d is concentration detected of total drug

C_f is concentration of free drug.

The entrapment efficiency was obtained by repeating the experiment in triplicate and the values were expressed as mean standard deviation.

Trapped volume is an important parameter that governs the encapsulation efficiency and morphology of vesicles. The internal or trapped volume is the aqueous entrapped volume per unit quantity of lipid and expressed as µl/µmol or µl/mg of total lipid.

APPLICATION [3,2,8,26]

Applications of topical liposomes in medicine and pharmacology can be divided into diagnostic and therapeutic applications of liposomes containing various markers or drugs, and their use as a tool, a model, or reagent in the basic studies of cell interactions, recognition processes, and mode of action of certain substances. Unfortunately, many drugs have a very narrow therapeutic window, meaning that the therapeutic concentration is not much lower than the toxic one. In several cases, the toxicity can be reduced or the efficacy can be enhanced by the use of a suitable drug carrier which alters the temporal and spatial delivery of the drug, i.e., its biodistribution and pharmacokinetics. It is clear from many pre-clinical and clinical studies that drugs, for instance antitumor drugs, parceled in liposome demonstration reduced toxicities, while retentive enhanced efficacy [29].

Protection against enzyme degradation of drugs:

Topical liposomes are used to protect the entrapped drug against enzymatic degradation. The basis is that lipid is used in there formulation are nit susceptible to enzymatic degradation. The entrapped drug is protected while the lipid vesicles are in circulation in extra cellular fluid.

Treatment of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infections:

Several antiretroviral nucleotide analogues have been developed for the treatment of patients suffering from the acquired immunodeficiency syndromes (AIDS). These include antisense oligonucleotide, which is a new antiviral agent that has shown potential therapeutic application against HIV-1.

Drug Targeting:

The approach of drug targeting via topical liposomes involved the use of ligands (for examples; antibodies, sugar residue, hormones) which are tagged on the lipid vesicles. The ligand recognizes specific receptor sites and thus causes the lipid vesicles to concentrate at such targeting site. By this approach otherwise distribution of topical liposomes into the reticuloendothelial system (liver, spleen and bone marrow) is minimized.

Topical drug delivery system:

The topical liposomes on the skin surface has been proven to be effective in drug delivery into the skin. Topical liposomes increase the permeability of skin of various entrapped drugs at the same time diminish the side effect of these drugs.

Enhanced antimicrobial efficacy:

They protect the entrapped drug against enzymatic degradation. For instance the penicillin and cephalosporin are sensitive to degradative action of β -lactamase, which is produced by a certain micro-organism. On the other hand the lipid nature of the vesicles promote enhance the cellular uptake of the antibiotic into the micro-organism, thus reducing the effective dose and incidence of the toxicity as exemplified by the liposomal formulation of amphoterracin B.

Anticancer therapy:

Numerous different liposome formulations of numerous anticancer agents were shown to be less toxic than the free drug. Anthracyclines are drugs which stop the growth of dividing cells by intercalating into the DNA and, thus, kill mainly rapidly dividing cells. These cells are not only in tumors but are also in hair, gastrointestinal mucosa, and blood cells; therefore, this class of drug is very toxic. The most used and studied is Adriamycin. In addition to the above-mentioned acute toxicities, its dosage is limited by its increasing cardio toxicity. In most cases, the toxicity was reduced to about 50%. These include both acute and chronic toxicities because liposome encapsulation reduces the delivery of the drug molecules towards those tissues. For the same reason, the efficiency was in many cases compromised due to the reduced bioavailability of the drug, especially if the tumor was not phagocytic or located in the organs of mononuclear phagocytic system. In some cases, such as systemic lymphoma, the effect of liposome encapsulation showed enhanced efficacy due to the continued release effect, i.e., longer presence of therapeutic concentrations in the circulation, while in several other cases, the sequestration of the drug into tissues of mononuclear phagocytic system actually reduced its efficacy [32-34].

CONCLUSION

Topical liposomes have some advantages which make them look interesting as drug carriers for topically applied drugs. They can act as sustained release depots, releasing encapsulated drugs of half-lives ranging from 0.6 to 11 days. This indeed might mean a greater possibility to control the drug release. The topically applied liposomal formulations, particularly those prepared from lipid mixtures of composition similar to the stratum corneum, would be an effective delivery system for the treatment of skin diseases. Since these liposomal formulations provide sustained, enhanced levels in deeper strata of the skin, they have the capacity to meter a sufficient quantity of drug into deeper tissue to treat the skin symptomology. It also reduce the incidence of undesirable side effects arising from systemic administration, or enhanced systemic absorption of drug.

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